

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

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fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

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muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
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- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLAR BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENTNING TASHKILYI MODELLARI.....	26
Madaminov Bekzod Allayarovich	
“HUDUDGAZTA‘MINOT” AJ DA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN LOYIHALAR SAMARASI	32
Shukurillaev Jahongir Botir o‘g‘li	
HARBIY XIZMATCHI AYOLLARNING MAXSUS KIYIM SIFATIGA QO‘YILADIGAN DASTLABKI TALABLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH	37
Abduraxmanova N.D., Mirtolipova N.X., Nasirullayeva G.S.	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ НЕСПЕЦИФИЧЕСКОГО ЯЗВЕННОГО КОЛИТА У ДЕТЕЙ	42
Закирова Бахора Исламовна, Каримов Достон Рустам угли	
ОЦЕНКА ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ФИСКАЛЬНЫХ И КРЕДИТНЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ НА РЫНКИ ВЫСОКОЛИКВИДНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ И ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ МОНОПОЛИЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	48
Бекзод Умматов	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА.....	55
Вахидов Азизжон Саиджонович	
SUG‘URTA FAOLIYATIDAGI MOLIYAVIY RISKLAR: BAHOLASH VA MINIMALLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	58
Xalikulova Shirin Utkir qizi	
“ANDIJONDONMAHSULOT” AJ MISOLIDA XARAJATLARNING STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBİ: AMALIY TAHLIL VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH TAVSIYALARI	62
Xayitboyeva Laylo Oybekovna	
XORIJİY MAMLAKATLARNING NORASMIY IQTISODIYOT DARAJASINI PASAYTIRISHDAGI TAJRIBASI	66
Alimardonov G‘ayratjon Nuraliyevich	
XO‘JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA BARQARORLIK HISOBOTLARI AUDITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	72
Xolikov Ravshan Anvar o‘g‘li	
PUL - KREDIT SIYOSATINING TRANSMISSION MEXANIZMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	76
Obidova Zilola Ikromjon qizi	
HOMILADORLIK DAVRIDA AYOLLARDA UCHRAYDIGAN GESTOZLI KATARAL GINGIVITNI KOMPLEKS DAVOLASHNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	81
Nomurodova Farangiz Lazizovna	
AGRAR KORXONALARDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHDA INVESTITSIYA MEXANIZMLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	87
Egamberdiyev Abdujabbor Xusanovich	
YOSHLAR TADBIRKORLIGI VA KICHIK BIZNES IQTISODIYOTINI TA‘MINLASHDA INFRATUZILMALARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	92
Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINING MAZMUNI VA TAMOIYILLARI	96
Mavrulov Ravshan Nematjonovich	

УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫМИ КОММУНИКАЦИЯМИ В ПРОЕКТАХ	101
Носирова Гулираъно Абдулазиз кизи	
DAVLAT BUDJETI JARAYONIDA MONITORING VA MOLIVAVIY NAZORATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	107
Yax'yayeva Dilfuza Bagdatovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	111
Axmedov Sanjar Temur o'g'li	
RAQAMLI MOLIVA TEXNOLOGIYALARI EVOLYUTSIYASINING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI VA YUZAGA KELISHI MUMKIN BO'LGAN XATARLAR TAHLILI	117
Ko'chimov Jahongir Shuxrat o'g'li	
GAZ VA GAZ KONDENSATINI YIG'ISH VA TAYYORLASH TIZIMLARI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY LOYIHALASH USULLARI TAHLILI	123
Abdirazakov Akmal Ibragimovich Namozov Og'abek Maxmud o'g'li	
AGILE PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA: STRATEGIES, FRAMEWORKS, AND BEST PRACTICES FOR SUCCESS	128
Utkirova Maftuna Murodjon qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORTYOR KORXONALARINING YANGI BOZORLARGA CHIQISHIDA FAOL MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	134
Baqoyev Sunnatillo Burxon o'g'li	
TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATIGA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	139
Salaydinov Shodiyor Nizom o'g'li	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY JIHLTLARI	144
Qurbonov Jasurbek Pozilovich	
OPTIMIZATION OF ROADSIDE AUTO CAMPING SITES (REST AREAS) ON HIGHWAYS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: INFRASTRUCTURE GAPS AND CORRIDOR-BASED EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	150
Akramov Akbarjon Akmal ugli	
QURILISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION MARKETING YONDASHUVLARINING AHAMIYATI	156
Aminov Abbas Mo'minboy o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA AHOLI ISH BILAN BANDLIGI SAMARADORLIGINI IFODALOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR	160
Abdusaidov Akmal Abduvaliyevich	
MINTAQADA XUSUSIY TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYASI	165
Yakubov Temur G'anibekovich	
AHOLI DEMOGRAFIK JARAYONLARINI IFODALOVCHI STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI	169
Siroj Zarina Rustambekovna	
AXBOROT MAHSULOTLARI BIZNESINING YAIM VA BANDLIKKA TA'SIRI: EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL	176
Abdullayev Abdulla Fayzulla o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	181
Ziyodullayev Qahramon	
ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ: ПОЛЬЗА ДЛЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ И ЭКОЛОГИИ	185
Хамдамова Гавхар Абсаматовна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISHNING MOLIVAVIY VOSITALARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI	191
Mamatov Baxodir Quldoshovich	

KO'P QIRRALI VALLARNING SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI VA USULLARINI TAHLIL QILISH	197
<i>Xasanov Bobirmirzo Maxmudali o'g'li, Valixonov Dostonbek Azim o'g'li, Alibekov Rasulbek Qanotbek o'g'li</i>	
MINTAQA SANOATINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELASHTIRISH	205
<i>Abdinazarov Xusan Shaymanovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH	209
<i>Nomozova Qumri Isoyevna</i>	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR TALABLARI ASOSIDA AUDITORLIK TEKSHIRUVINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	216
<i>Akromov Shohrux Shuhrat o'g'li</i>	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINING RIVOJLANISHNI TARTIBGA SOLISH TIZIMI	221
<i>Achilova Firuza Kurbanovna</i>	
BANK MENEJMENTIDA INKLYUZIV MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI, TAMOYILLARI VA STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI	225
<i>Rajabov Oybek Panjievich</i>	
MINTAQADA OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELASHTIRISH	229
<i>Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
MAISHIY XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION KLASTER MODELINI JORIY ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	235
<i>Normurodova Zebo Eshmaxmatovna</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH	240
<i>Xatamov Nurbek Ochildiyevich, Sharifi Abdul Fatah</i>	
MOLIYAVIY REJALASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI YECHIMI YUZASIDAN TAKLIFLAR	245
<i>Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI LIKVIDLIK RISKLARINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	251
<i>Sulaymanov Samandarboy Adhambek o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	257
<i>Karimov Shohrux Boydulla o'g'li</i>	
"O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATINING HISOBOTLARINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH	262
<i>Astanov Zafar Murodillayevich</i>	
QARAMA-QARSHI AYLANUVCHI IKKI ROTORLI SHAMOL TURBINASINING MATEMATIK MODEL	266
<i>Pirmatov Nurali Berdiyevich, Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Saodullayev Abror Saypullayevich, Qurbonov Najmiddin Abduxamidovich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INSTITUTIONAL VA INVESTITSION MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	272
<i>Norboev Sarvar Azodovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TRANSPORT SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	277
<i>Jaloliddinov Anvar Jaloliddin o'g'li</i>	
ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN'S MAIN ECONOMIC INDICATORS AND GDP GROWTH	283
<i>B.Beknazarov</i>	

SOTISH JARAYONIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARINING INTEGRATSIIYASI	288
Abduxalilova Laylo Tohtasinovna	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В АУДИТЕ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ И УЗБЕКСКИЙ КОНТЕКСТ	294
Мегноров Алмардон Абдирахмонович	
RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN UNCERTAIN ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENTS: A GLOBAL COMPARATIVE STUDY	302
Nigmatova Malika	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	307
Hamrayev Maqsudjon Saidaxmadovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	311
Mamajonova Gulbaxor Toxirjon qizi	
АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ АУДИТОРСКИХ ПРОЦЕДУР НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ: ВЛИЯНИЕ НА КАЧЕСТВО АУДИТОРСКИХ ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЙ	316
Киличева Ф.Б.	
MAISHIY TEXNIKA EKSPORTIDA YASHIL IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	320
Kushmanova Mahbuba	
GAZ TA'MINOTIDA YO'QOTISHLARNI KAMAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY ASOSLARI	324
Xamidov Xayriddin Faxritdinovich	
DAVLAT AKTIVLARINI XUSUSIYLASHTIRISHNING MINTAQA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	329
Sharapov Farrux Shomuratovich	
КРИТЕРИИ ОТБРАКОВКИ ЭКСТРУЗИОННЫХ АЛЮМИНИЕВЫХ ПРОФИЛЕЙ ГРУППЫ ALMGS1 ПО МАКРОСТРУКТУРНЫМ ПРИЗНАКАМ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ	333
Ибрахимов Фаррухжон Фарходович	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA DEBITORLIK QARZLARI VA FAKTORING OPERATSIYALARI HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	336
G'oziyeva Mokhira Rustamovna	
KULTIVATOR YUMSHATKICH PANJALARI O'TMASLANISH DARAJASINING ISH KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	345
Quvondiqov Yoqub Tursunbaevich, Nuraliyev To'liqin Alimardanovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION STRATEGIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR	352
To'g'onov Ibroximxo'ja	
TMK KORXONASI SHAROITIDA R6AM5 MARKALI TEZKESAR PO'LATDAN TAYYORLANGAN PARMA UCHUN TERMIK ISHLOV BERISH REJIMI	358
Djalalova Sevara Toxtamuratovna	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ	362
Шоев Алим Халмуратович	
TRANSFORMATSIYA VA XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH OMILLARINING BANK SAMARADORLIGI KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	367
Umirzoqova Aziza Olim qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	372
Ismatov Raxmatilla Oltinovich	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARI TADBIRKORLIK SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	376
Yoqubjonov Ibrohim G'olibjon o'g'li	

BANK TIZIMIDAGI AKTIVLARINING UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH BO'YICHA STRATEGIK YONDASHUVLAR	379
Sadikov Q.M.	
СЦЕНАРНОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОТРАСЛЕЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ НЕОПРЕДЕЛЁННОСТИ И СТРУКТУРНЫХ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЙ	383
Муслимова Ф.С., Хашимова Н.А.	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLARNI TAQDIM QILISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI	390
S.M. Raximova	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI AXBOROT-RESURS MARKAZLARI FAOLIYATINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH MODELI	395
Qurbanova Muazzam Fazliddinova	
IQTISODIYOTNING TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUVI JARAYONIDA INVESTITSION KREDITLASHNING TAHLILI	399
Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH MASALALARI	404
Abdug'aniyev Murodjon Shavkat o'g'li	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARNING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI INVESTITSIYALAR YORDAMIDA QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH	408
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FRANSUZ TILIDA FE'L SEMANTIKASINING KO'PMA'NOLILIK VA BIRMA'NOLILIK ASPEKTLARI	412
Jo'rayeva Malohat Muhammadovna, Bekmetova Munisa Karimbayevna	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA ASOSIY KAPITALGA KIRITILGAN INVESTISIYALARDA CHET-EL INVESTISIYASI VA KREDITLARINI ROLI	418
Sultanov Anvar Abdullaevich	
INSON QON TOMIRLARINING TARMOQLANISHINI L-SISTEMALAR ASOSIDA HOSIL QILISH ALGORITMNI ISHLAB CHIQISH	423
Boliyeva Dilrabo Nurbek qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT LOYIHALARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK (DXSH)NING AHAMIYATI	429
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA TURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI	434
Otaylor Usmonaliyev	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA VALYUTA ARBITRAJI VA UNING MOHIYATI	440
Yaxyayev Ziyodilla Lutfullayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN ALOQA SOHASINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	443
Mirzaraximova Aziza Azimdjanovna	
DON VA UN MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH XUSUSIYATLARI	450
Boyjigitov Sanjarbek Komiljon o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA TUXUM ISHLAB CHIQARISHNING JORIY HOLATI TAHLILI	454
Ismoilov Zuhridin Sayitqulovich	
ZAMONAVIY TURAR-JOY ME'MORCHILIGIDA MILLIYLIK VA AN'ANAVIYLIKNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	459
Toshniyozov Otabek Hakimovich	
MARKAZIY QIZILQUM FOSFORIT RUDALARIDAN QIMMATBAHO KOMPONENTLARNI KOMPLEKS AJRATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI	464
Eshonqulov Uchqun Xudaynazar o'g'li, Ruzibayeva Dildora Akramovna, Xushvaqtova Dilshoda Shavkat qizi	

BANKLARDA CHAKANA KREDITLASH JARAYONLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TARTIBI	470
Axmedova Dilrabo Kurbondurdi qizi	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESNI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING XALQARO MODELLARI HAMDA ULARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI	476
Nodirbek Shavkatovich Mirzaaxmedov	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATIDA XOTIN-QIZLARNING BOSHQARUV KARYERASI: MOHIYATI, ZARURIYATI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	483
Abduraxmonova Feruzabonu	
ASOSIY KAPITALGA INVESTITSİYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI	489
Xoshimov Sobir Murtazayevich	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINING TASHKILY TUZILMASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	495
Uzakova Umida Ruziyevna	
OLIY TA‘LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI VA PROFESSOR-O‘QITUVCHI–TALABA NISBATI O‘RTASIDAGI IQTISODIY BOG‘LIQLIK.....	502
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В СИСТЕМЫ AML: АНАЛИЗ ПРАКТИК ВЕДУЩИХ БАНКОВ И СТРАН СНГ	507
Рашидов Авазбек Рахимович	
BOJXONA TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHDAGI MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR TAHLILI	516
Radjapova Latofat Sardorovna	
DEFORMATSİYALANUVCHAN STANDART CHIZIQLI QATTIQ (STANDARD LINEAR SOLID MODEL, SLS) MODEL ISHLAB CHIQISH VA SONINI TAHLIL QILISH	523
Ahmadov Ilhom Aktam o‘g‘li, Faxriddinova Rayhona Vahobjon qizi, Rustamova Ruxsora Kamtar qizi	
ВЛИЯНИЕ КЕРАМИЧЕСКИХ КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ ПОКРЫТИЙ НА ТЕПЛОВУЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ КАМЕННОГО ТЕПЛОАККУМУЛЯТОРА В СОЛНЕЧНО-АССИСТИРОВАННЫХ БИОГАЗОВЫХ УСТАНОВКАХ	530
Д.М. Жураханов	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY MOLIYA TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KELAJAKDAGI IMKONIYATLARI.....	537
Akbarov Husniddinjon Mo‘ysin o‘g‘li	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLARNI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA OCHIQLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISH	544
Xolmirzayev Ulug‘bek Abdulazizovich, Normatov Joxongir Murodillayevich	
DON MAHSULOTLARI TARMOG‘IDA ISHLAB CHIQARISH QUVVATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	548
Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
BUXORO VILOYATI SANOATI ISHLAB CHIQARISHINING TARMOQ TARKIBI DINAMIKASI VA UNDAGI O‘ZGARISHLAR TAHLILI	554
Toshov Mirzabek Hakimovich	
TEMIR YO‘L TRANSPORTINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEZONLARI	560
Nurxo‘jayeva Xilola Hakimxo‘jayevna	
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ УГОЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТЬЮ НА ОСНОВЕ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА	568
Teshaboyev To‘lqin Zakirovich, Muradov Botir Xayat	
IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARIDA SUV ISTE‘MOLINING BOSHQARUVINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	578
Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich, Turg‘unov Muhammadaziz Baxtiyorjon o‘g‘li	
SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MOBIL ILOVALAR ASOSIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	584
Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich, Uzakov Sirojiddin Djuraboyevich	

SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA IQTISODIYOTNING O'ZARO ALOQADORLIGI	591
Sobirov Abdurasul Abdugafarovich	
IDENTIFICATION OF WEAVING STRUCTURES IN PILE FABRICS	596
Bahrom Baturovich Dautov, Bakhtiyor Yormakhmatovich Abduganiyev, Erkin Shamsiddinovich Rayxonov, Nazar Kilichov Bafoevich	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	602
Otajanova Shahnoza Shuhratovna	
AXBOROT-RESURS MARKAZLARI FAOLIYATI VA OLIY TA'LIM SIFATI KO'RSATKICHLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK MASALALARI	608
Pirmedova Xayitgul Muxammedovna	
TIJORAT BANKLAR FAOLIYATIDA DAROMADLAR VA UNING AHAMIYATI	613
Kenjayev M.G'	
MAJBURIYATLAR AUDITINING ASOSIY O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	618
Ergasheva Vasila Abdumajitovna	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA OLIY TA'LIM EKSPORT XIZMATLARI MOLIYAVIY NATIJADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	623
Abdusattarova Dildora Bohodirovna	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING INSTITUTSIONAL MEXANIZMLARI TAHLILI	630
Djurayeva Lola Abdugabbarovna	
JAMOAT YO'LOVCHI TRANSPORTINI YO'NALISHLARDA HARAKATI MUNTAZAMLIGIGA TA'SIR KO'RSATUVCHI OMILLAR	635
Nazarov Anvar Aripovich, Siddiqov Beknazar Jumanazar o'g'li	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	643
Ismatullayeva Munisxon Bori qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YAKKA TARTIBDAGI TADBIRKORLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: 2026-YIL ISLOHOTLARI VA RAQAMLI MA'MURCHILIK	649
Yakubov San'atbek Ravshanbekovich	
ISHLAB CHIQRISH SANOATI CHIQINDILARIDAN LITIY BIRIKMALARINI AJRATIB OLIISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIK YECHIMLARI	655
Eshonqulov Uchqun Xudaynazar o'g'li, Komilov Botir Asqar o'g'li	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARINING MOLIYAVIY RISKLARINI BAHOLASHDA MIQDORIY USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH	663
Raximov Abduxalil Toshbotirovich	
JUN TOLASINI MAYDA VA YIRIK IFLOSLIKlardan TOZALASH TEXNOLOGIYASI VA USKUNALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	669
Omonturdiyev Ortiq Eshboyevich	
O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDA KASB-HUNAR TA'LIMI TERMINLARINING SEMANTIK QIYOSIY TAHLILI	673
Jabbarova Gulbahor Jumanazarovna	
GAZ BALLONLI AVTOMOBILLARDA RADIOTO'LQINLI UZATMALAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRILGAN TEXNIK NAZORAT TIZIMINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	677
Mirzayev Bahodir Nuritdinovich, Zulfiqorova Guldon Akbarjon qizi	
MINTAQANING TASHQI SAVDO AYLANMASINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH USULLARI	682
G'oyibnazarov Muxammad Xamidbekovich	
IQTISODIY TADQIQOTLARDA SO'ROV O'TKAZISH METODI VA UNING ANKETA HAMDA INTERVYU SHAKLLARINI QO'LLASH MASALALARI	687
Dusmurov Radjabbay Davlatbayevich	

O'ZBEKISTONDA AUDITORLIK FAOLIYATI RIVOJLANISHI VA BIZNESDA MANFAATLAR UYG'UNLIGI.....	693
Sirojiddinov Ikromiddin Qutbiddinovich	
DAVLAT MOLIYASI VA BANK-MOLIYA INSTITUTLARINING IQTISODIY O'SISHDAGI O'RNI.....	698
Sayitbayev Shermirza Datkamirzaevich	
TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUV SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI RESURS BAZASINI MUSTAHKAMLASH YO'NALISHLARI	703
Xolmatov Dilmurod Maxmudjonovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI: AN'ANAVIY BANKING TIZIMIDAN NEOBANKLARGA O'TISH MUAMMOLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	711
Shokirov Sardor Inotdullo o'g'li	
AVTOMATIK LOKOMATIV SIGNALIZATSIYA KODLARINI UZATISH VA DESHIFRATSIYALASH QURILMASI ISHINI TAHLIL QILISH VA DASTURIY TA'MINOTINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH.....	718
Raxmonov Bobomurod Baxtiyorovich, Qodirov Izzatjon Abrorjon o'g'li	
ФИНАНСОВАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УСКОРЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ ЧЕРЕЗ ОПТИМИЗАЦИЮ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ СТАРТАП-ПРОЕКТОВ В ВУЗАХ	724
Касимова Наргиза Сабитджановна	
KORXONALARDA PUL OQIMLARINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGI VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIK O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK	729
Omonov Otajon Juraqulovich	
INVESTITSIYALAR VA INNOVATSION FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARNING ILG'OR TAJRIBALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	734
Gafurova Umida Fatixovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI HAMDA ULARNING YECHIMLARI BO'YICHA AMALGA OSHIRILAYOTGAN ISHLAR TAHLILI.....	740
Bekmetov Xursandbek Iloxamovich	
THE INTEGRATION OF TRADITION AND INNOVATION IN WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN: ECONOMIC MECHANISMS AND STRATEGIC APPROACHES	747
Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna	
KO'TARILGAN TEMIR YO'L ESTAKADASIDA VAGONDAN KO'MIR TUSHIRISH JARAYONIDA CHANG TARQALISHINI BAHOLASH	757
Tohtemirov Inomjon Muqimjonovich, Xudayberganov Sakijan Kabildjanovich	
DUMKAR TIPIDAGI VAGONLARDAN YUKLARNI TUSHURISH VAQTIDA ULARNING AG'DARILISHINI OLDINI OLUVCHI TAKOMILLASHTIRILGAN QURILMANING ILMIY ASOSLARI.....	762
Yusupov Azizjon Qahramonovich, Normoxmatov Bekzodjon Shovkat o'g'li	
TEMIR YO'L STANTSIYALARIDA ARALASH POYEZDLAR HARAKATI UCHUN AVTOMATIK MARSHRUTNI SOZLASH USULI	769
Boltayev Sunnatillo Tuymurodovich, Raxmonov Bobomurod Baxtiyorovich, Kasimova Qamara Amonovna	
O'ZBEKISTON MAHSULOTLARINI XORIJIY BOZORLAR UCHUN TAYYORLASHDA FRANCHAYZING ASOSIDA NUFUZLI BRENDLAR BILAN HAMKORLIK VA QO'SHMA LOYIHALAR MEXANIZMINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH.....	777
Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	
AKSIONERLIK JAMIYATLARDA MOLIYAVIY INVESTITSIYALAR HISOB VA AUDITINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA YURITISH.....	783
Suyunov Yorqin Bekmurodovich	
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY INDICATORS OF DIESEL ENGINES BY IMPROVING THE COOLING SYSTEM	789
Khushnaye Obid, Orakbaeva Guljakhon	

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY INDICATORS OF DIESEL ENGINES BY IMPROVING THE COOLING SYSTEM

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Abstract. The paper investigates methods for improving the performance of diesel engines through the optimization of the cooling system. Particular attention is paid to the thermal load increase observed when spark-ignition engines are converted to operate on natural gas. Experimental studies were conducted on a gas-fueled engine installed in a diesel-gas microbus. The results highlight the importance of optimizing the temperature regime of gas engines. Based on the analysis, design and operational recommendations are proposed to improve the cooling system, enabling a reduction in cooling temperature from 120 °C to 90 °C.

Keywords: cooling systems, performance indicators, spark ignition, gaseous fuel, fuel and economic indicators.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada dizel dvigatellarini ish samaradorligini sovitish tizimini optimallashtirish orqali oshirish usullari tadqiq etilgan. Ayniqsa, uchqun bilan o't oldiriladigan dvigatellarni tabiiy gazda ishlashga o'tkazishda kuzatiladigan issiqlik yuklamasining ortishiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Eksperimental tadqiqotlar dizel-gaz mikroavtobusiga o'rnatilgan gaz yonilg'isida ishlovchi dvigatelda olib borildi. Olingan natijalar gaz dvigatellarida harorat rejimini optimallashtirish muhimligini ko'rsatadi. Tahlil asosida sovitish tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha konstruktiv va ekspluatatsion tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi, bu esa sovitish haroratini 120 °C dan 90 °C gacha pasaytirish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: sovutish tizimi, effektiv ko'rsatkichlar, uchqun bilan o't oldirish, gazsimon yonilg'i, yonilg'ilar, iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются методы повышения эффективности дизельных двигателей за счёт оптимизации системы охлаждения. Особое внимание уделяется увеличению тепловой нагрузки, наблюдаемой при переводе двигателей с искровым зажиганием на работу на природном газе. Экспериментальные исследования были проведены на газовом двигателе, установленном на дизельно-газовом микроавтобусе. Полученные результаты подчёркивают важность оптимизации температурного режима газовых двигателей. На основе проведённого анализа предложены конструктивные и эксплуатационные рекомендации по совершенствованию системы охлаждения, позволяющие снизить температуру охлаждения с 120 °C до 90 °C.

Ключевые слова: системы охлаждения, показатели эффективности, искровое зажигание, газообразное топливо, топливные и экономические показатели.

INTRODUCTION

Taking into account the global trend toward the widespread use of natural gas as an alternative fuel for automotive transport, especially buses and minibuses equipped with spark-ignition engines, the problem of improving engine cooling systems becomes particularly relevant. The transition of engines to natural gas operation is accompanied by changes in the working process, which often lead to an increase in thermal stress on engine components. Therefore, it is necessary to address a number of key scientific and technical challenges, including the analysis of cooling system designs and operating processes, identification of the

causes of increased thermal loads on engine parts during conversion to gas fuel, and the development of effective measures aimed at enhancing cooling system performance.

LITERATURE VIEW

Numerous researchers have contributed to the study of cooling systems of automobile and transport engines, including Gureev A.A., Grigorev M.A., Kavtaradze R.Z., Kostin A.K., Levin M.I., Liventsev F.L., Lukov N.M., Nikolenko A.V., Petrichenko R.M., Petrichenko M.R., Razuvaev A.V., and others. Their works mainly focus on the influence of coolant temperature on engine heat intensity, power output, fuel efficiency, wear resistance, as well as the specific features of engine operation and improvement of cooling efficiency under high-altitude and hot climate conditions. However, despite the significant volume of research, only a limited number of studies are devoted to spark-ignition internal combustion engines operating on gaseous fuels, which highlights the insufficient investigation of this issue.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The development of modern engine design is closely associated with increasing specific power, improving fuel economy, and meeting stringent environmental requirements. These trends inevitably lead to a rise in the thermal intensity of the main components forming the combustion chamber, primarily due to changes in heat transfer conditions. The expansion of temperature limits within the engine operating cycle results in increased thermal loads on critical components, while simultaneously contributing to a reduction in harmful emissions in exhaust gases.

It is well established that most modern internal combustion engines operate under thermal conditions close to optimal only at nominal operating modes. Even under these conditions, the temperatures of engine components and systems do not always correspond to optimal values from the standpoint of maximum efficiency. This is largely explained by the need to maintain a temperature reserve to ensure reliability in case of deviations in cooling system parameters. Under partial load conditions, which are characteristic of real-world vehicle operation, deviations of component and system temperatures from optimal values become more pronounced due to insufficient control of the engine thermal regime [1].

One of the most promising approaches to reducing harmful emissions and improving fuel and economic performance of automobile engines is the enhancement of the working process through the use of alternative fuels combined with the optimization of temperature regimes of engine systems and components. The temperature of highly thermally loaded parts, such as the cylinder and cylinder head, as well as the temperatures of coolant, lubricating oil, fuel, and intake air, have a significant influence on the technical, economic, and environmental performance of engines.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

For diesel and spark-ignition engines, the coolant temperature at the engine outlet (T_{co}) and the oil temperature (T_o) are typically maintained within the ranges of 350-365 K and 340-360 K, respectively [2, 3]. Maintaining these parameters within optimal limits is especially critical for gas-fueled engines, where deviations can lead to increased thermal stress and reduced durability.

Taking into account the methods and methodologies of the conducted theoretical researches with the use of the mathematical apparatus of the regression analysis realized on the ECM, the maintenance tests have been carried out.

Practical significance and implementation of the research results consist in recommendations to improve the cooling system and to reveal the specific effect of cooling system temperatures on the power and fuel and economic performance of the engine with spark ignition when operating on gas fuel.

Scientific novelty of the research was indicated on the basis of the research and practical analysis of cooling systems of automobile engines with different power systems operating on diesel or gas, scientifically substantiated improvement of the cooling system, which allows reducing the thermal stress of engine parts and improving its performance.

The structure and composition of the work include the identified and studied problems related to the operation of gas-powered buses and minibus engines, the results of theoretical and experimental research on the selected subject.

Design features of gas engines

Gas fuel has evolved from an alternative to a separate type of motor fuel. The first deep theoretical and experimental studies of automotive gas equipment date back to the pre-war and post-war period. They were devoted to the analysis of stable operation and regulation of gas pressure, as well as the study of its impact on

the operation of the gas engine. As a result, the basis for calculating gas-cylinder equipment (GCE) was laid down.

Analysis of the operation of modern engine cooling systems

The cooling system is designed for forced removal of heat from engine parts flowing with hot gases to ensure their optimal and stable thermal condition [5].

Depending on the way the heat exchange between the engine elements and the environment is organized, there are systems with intermediate coolant (liquid cooling circulating systems) and systems without intermediate coolant (air cooling systems and liquid cooling flow system).

Flow-through liquid cooling system is structurally the easiest to manufacture and operate (Fig. 1). On the ground transport the circulation two-circuit systems where heat removal is carried out in air, and a cooling liquid is used as the intermediate heat-carrier circulating on the closed contour have received the greatest distribution.

The design of the liquid cooling system is largely determined by the accepted way of organizing the circulation of liquid. According to the abovementioned feature there are systems: thermosiphon systems, with forced circulation of liquid and mixed cooling systems.

Fig.1. Principle diagram of liquid cooling flow system:

1 - Inlet box; 2 - filter; 5 - check valve; 4 - pump; 5 - mains line supply of water to the engine; 6 - mainline water output engine; 7 - controlled valve; 8 - engine; 9 - temperature gauge; 10 - control unit

Fig.2. Principle scheme of the thermosiphon cooling system:

1 - Radiator; 2 - fan; 3 - cylinder block; 4 - coolant supply hose from the radiator to the cylinder block; 5 - coolant drain hose from the cylinder block to the radiator

In a thermosiphon system (Fig. 2), liquid circulation occurs due to the difference in temperature and density in different areas of the liquid circuit. Such cooling system is the simplest and most inexpensive, but at its acceptable dimensions, thermomechanical is not sufficiently effective. For intensive circulation of liquid in it, a significant temperature difference of Δt_i on the radiator (about $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) is required. Otherwise, low liquid velocities can lead to local overheating and significant temperature gradients in the cooled engine elements.

Due to the noted deficiencies in modern transport ICE, thermosiphon cooling systems are not used. The system with forced circulation of the cooling agent is currently one of the main types of cooling systems for auto-tractor engines. Forced circulation of the intermediate coolant along the entire circuit is carried out by the liquid pump 6 (Fig. 3). The cooling agent is supplied through the lower zone of the cylinders [5].

Fig.3. Principle scheme of the circulating liquid cooling system:

1 - Radiator; 2 - steam-air tube; 3 - thermostat; 4 - expansion tank; 5 - expansion tank plug; 6 - liquid pump; 7 - cylinder block jacket; 8 - Fan; 9 - bypass line

Mixed cooling systems (Fig. 4 a, b) the coolant from radiator 1 is supplied to the upper zone of the cylinder cooling jacket (Fig. 4 a) or to the cavity of the block head (Fig. 4 b), or to the cavity of the block head (Fig. 4 b). In the latter case, the engine cylinders are cooled by the thermosiphon effect. When the coolant is supplied to the block head, sometimes (with large linear engine sizes) the distribution pipes 10 are used (Fig. 4 b), which allow intensifying the cooling of the hottest areas of the combustion chambers. Such systems are mainly used on spark-ignition engines.

Fig.4. Scheme of mixed liquid cooling systems:

a - with liquid supply to the upper belt of the cylinder cooling jacket; b - with liquid supply to the cavity of the block head; c - two-cavity cooling system; 1 - radiator; 2 - liquid pump; 3 - single-valve thermostat; 4 - engine cooling jacket; 5 - fan; 6 - bypass line; 7 - two-valve thermostat; 8 - main thermostat valve; 9 - optional thermostat valve; 10 - distribution pipe; 11 - upper cylinder cooling cavity; 12 - lower cylinder cooling cavity; 13 - coolant supply length channel; 14 - partition

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Therefore, in the process of improving the performance of diesel engines by enhancing the cooling system, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Analyze the design features of gas engines;
2. Analyze the operation principles of modern engine cooling systems;

3. Carry out theoretical research of the cooling system of gas-powered buses and minibus engines, which would allow to reveal the reasons leading to the increase of thermal stress of the engine parts during conversion to gas fuel, which consists in the specifics and peculiarities of the working process;
4. Suggest ways to improve the gas engine cooling system;
5. Develop and propose variants for improvement of gas engine cooling system, which will reduce the cooling temperature from 120 to 90 °C.

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